

Coastal Water Purification Strategies for Agricultural Needs at South 24 Parganas, West Bengal (WB)

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Abstract: The extensive coastline of India includes the South 24 Parganas district measuring one hundred fifty-eight (158) kilometres. Situated near the Bay of Bengal, this region faces issues with high salinity levels in both surface and subsurface water. Data from the Public Health Engineering Department indicates that, since 2017-2018, salinity, Total Dissolved Solids, and Chloride values in groundwater have significantly exceeded acceptable limits for irrigation water. The problem intensified after 2021-2022, adversely affecting the primary source of income for the residents of South 24 Parganas, which could be the agrarian economy. To address this issue and safeguard irrigation water from brackish contamination, recommendations include adopting adaptive agriculture systems, employing hybrid technologies for saline water, desalination, and distillation of brackish water. Among these methods, solar-powered desalination emerges as the most cost-effective solution for this rural and developing area.

Keywords: Coastal zone, agriculture, groundwater pollution, salinity, crop diversification

I. INTRODUCTION:

India possesses an extensive shoreline of seven thousand five hundred sixteen (7516) Km from which the mainland comprises five thousand four hundred twenty-two (5422) Km, the coastline of Lakshadweep stretches hundred thirty-two (132) Km and the Andaman & Nicobar Islands boast a coastal expanse of one thousand nine hundred sixty-two (1962) Km. Close to two hundred fifty (250) million individuals reside within proximity of fifty (50) Km from the shoreline. A population, urbanisation, and industrialisation surge have been noted in coastal areas of late. Coastal regions are observed by spontaneous human movement and anthropogenic activities. Consequently, the ecological balance of coastal zones throughout India has been disrupted. The eastern seaboard typically exhibits a gently sloping terrain featuring beaches, lagoons, deltas, and marshes. It is also positioned at a relatively low elevation with extensive alluvial plains and deltas. Additionally, the coastal area is rich in diverse coastal ecosystems such as coral reefs, mangroves, salt marshes, seagrasses, estuaries, lagoons, and dunes. The coastal region of India is enriched with natural resources which are advantageous due to the view point of both cost-effectiveness and environmental biology of India (Nayak 2017, Prof *et al* 2012). Due to the abundance of water, fresh air and other required resources for sustainable growth of the crops agricultural expansion is abundant in the coastal areas of India. (Kaur and Nandal 2020) This phenomenon has been noted on the eastern seaboard of India, including areas like South 24 Parganas. The investigation on the coastal region of South 24 Parganas is very useful now with the aid of land resource management practices (Dhiman 1999, Bandyopadhyay 2022).

India is a developing country. The main occupation of Indians is farming. An agricultural sector that utilizes 54.6% of total employment for the growing population accounts for more than ninety per cent of overall subsurface water usage in agriculture. (Fischer *et al* 2022). For prolonged years groundwater has been a major source of the agriculture sector for the sake of its self-sufficient access and prompt water supply. This excessive reliance on subsurface water has created a decline in the subsurface water table (WT) in A total of 64% of regions within India from the year 2002 to the year 2016. But now with the collaborative effort of government at different layers irrigation potential inclusive of surface as well as sub-surface aqua has enhanced to eighty-seven Mha and also conclusive farming capacity has marked hundred and forty Mha. Considering the current situation, and challenges in agriculture in India micro irrigation can play a decisive role in mitigating water demand in Shoreline farming (Jha *et al* 2022). Appropriately organized and governed sprinkler and drip irrigation methods have an efficiency of irrigation around 70% and 90% respectively in comparison to the surface irrigation method which has of efficiency 40% (Jain *et al* 2019, Mandal *et al* 2023).

Irrigation plays a pivotal role in farming. To yield high quantity and quality of crops high quality of irrigation is required. India possesses a substantial amount of groundwater, advantageous for irrigation in recent decades. In contrast to other states, WB stands as one of the most food-productive states in India. A substantial rank is held throughout India in terms of cropping intensity. In the case of WB subsurface irrigation is contemplated as a significant water resource. But due to urbanization groundwater in a few districts of WB is stressed.

From the data collected from the State Irrigation Department in the year 1987, it has been calculated that the entire presence of sub-surface water used in WB was 1.46-million-hectare meter Mha. The percentage of water requirements in WB distributed among various sectors in the years 2000 and 2011 have been evaluated. Based on past results the proportional water needs across different sectors in WB in the year 2025 has been estimated. All the results have been represented in Fig 1 below.

Fig 1 results the proportional water needs across different sectors in WB in 2000,2011 and 2025

From Fig 1 it has been observed that the agriculture sector has occupied the leading position in WB in terms of water requirements since 2000 but also fast progression of water requirements will be witnessed in coming years. At the beginning of this millennium 50% of water requirement is occupied by Agriculture. The figure for water requirement for agriculture in the year 2025 is expected to exceed more than 60% (Paul 2021)

II. LOCATION OF STUDY AREA:

Human growth has been observed enormous growth during the past 2000 years in India. It has been taking a rapid pace in the 20th century. The population evolution in South 24 Parganas reflects a consistent pattern of growth since the eighteenth century. The expansion of trade, commerce, industry, transportation, and employment opportunities has consistently been a key factor in attracting migrants, particularly in the northwestern part of the district and along the Hooghly River.

South 24 Parganas is recognized as the most extensive and second most densely populated district in WB, India. The district is positioned within the geographical coordinates of 21°29'00" Northing to 22°33'45" Northing latitude and 88°03'45" Easting to 89°04'50" Easting longitude. On 1st March 1986, 24 Parganas has been sculpted to create a fresh district viz. South 24 Parganas. The biggest district in terms of the area appears asymmetrical to the triangle. It possesses both man-made land borders and natural aquatic frontiers. To its North Kolkata is situated. To the North East of it North 24 Parganas is positioned. To the south of the district lies the Bay of Bengal (BoB).

Our study area is made up of twenty-nine (29) blocks surrounded by an international barrier with Bangladesh to its Eastern side. On the Western side of the district, the River Hooghly has outlined a barrier progressing from north to south that divides it from the districts of Howrah and Purba Medinipur (Mandal 2020). Our study area location map is depicted in Figure 2

Fig 2 Study area map

A publication from the WB Pollution Control Board in 2009 has revealed that groundwater recharge from precipitation was highest in South 24 Parganas. The replenishment of subsurface water from alternate sources in the study area was negligible. The entire picture of groundwater recharge in WB in the year 2009 has been represented in Fig 3.

III. ATMOSPHERIC PRECIPITATION IN THE STUDY SITE

The mean precipitation at South 24 Parganas surpasses that of WB. An investigation into the rainfall data from Indian Meteorological Department (IMD) over the past 14 years in the study area reveals Figure 3, illustrating that the highest rainfall occurred in 2013. However, the untimely procurement of precipitation data has led to irrigation problems, impacting subsurface water recharge in a distinct manner (Roy 2018).

Fig 3 Annual Rainfall value in South 24 Parganas from 2009-2023.

Irrigation in South 24 Parganas has occurred using both surface water and subsurface water. The primary origin of subsurface water is the infiltration of rainfall and recharge from various other sources (Bokke 2020, Kirby 2022, Wrachien *et al* 2021). Recharge from rainfall is typically high in the study area. Consequently, the primary source of irrigation in South 24 Parganas, which is groundwater, is adequately recharged due to precipitation, due to its high rate. The diagram of annual reprehensible groundwater resources over all the districts of WB is shown in Fig 4.

Fig 4 District-wise annual groundwater resources in Monsoon season in WB.

As depicted in Fig 3, it is apparent that there is an abundant supply of groundwater resources in South 24 Parganas. The replenishment primarily occurs through underground recharge, largely driven by rainfall. Consequently, this groundwater is readily accessible for irrigation in the study area.

IV. IRRIGATION STATUS IN SOUTH 24 PARGANAS

Agro-climatic zone of South 24 Parganas is positioned at the lower Gangetic plain region which is a coastal salty zone. The area of this largest district is more than 953,000 ha. Major lithology existing in the study area is clayey- loamy which is made up of saline alluvium. The net sown area present is more than 372,000 ha. For multiple cropping purposes, the area sown more than once is more than 158,000 ha. Gross cropped area exceeds 415,000 ha. Irrigation intensity in our study location is 30.91%. The area within the precipitation feed area is more than 256,000 ha. The socioeconomic categorisation of distinct blocks of South 24 Parganas, WB has been depicted in the table-1 below.

TABLE 1
SOCIAL-ECONOMIC CATEGORISATION OF DISTINCT BLOCKS OF SOUTH 24 PARGANAS, WB

Zone	Territory	Roles	Block Names
1	Northern-west Territory	Suburban region/ Partially transformed	Budge Budge I, Thakurpukur-Maheshtala, Budge Budge II, Sonarpur, Bishnupur I, Bishnupur II
2	Central-western and Northern East Territory	Evolving territory	Bhangar I, Bhangar II, Baruipur, Magrahat I, Magrahat II, Diamond Harbour I, Diamond Harbour II, Kulpi, Falta, Mandirabazar,
3	The Sundarban Region	Largely rural and disadvantaged zone	Basanti, Canning I, Canning II, Gosaba, Mathurapur I, Mathurapur II, Patharpratima, Joynagar I, Joynagar II, Kiltali, Sagar, Kakdwip, Namkhana,

A. Crop Concentration Index:

It has been observed that diversity in crop distribution is very high in South 24 Parganas. The meaning of crop concentration is fluctuation in crop distribution in a locality over a while. The abundance of a crop in a specific area is primarily influenced by factors such as its geographical extent, temperature, humidity, pricing and income levels, societal aspects, governmental policies, soil composition, and other relevant considerations. The most practised system of examining crop density is Bhatia’s position extract system. Bhatia (1965) has attempted to quantify the local characteristics of crop diversification. This method is very useful for interpreting anthropogenic activity over an area.

Mathematically is represented by equation no. (1)

$$c_x = (x / y)|(x' / y') \tag{1}$$

Wherein

- Cx= Index on crop concentration
- x= crop distribution in the specified region
- y= aggregate land devoted to all crops within the specified area
- x'= cultivated region for a particular crop in the designated area
- y'= aggregate cultivation across the entire region

B. Crop Diversity Index

Agricultural land use is principally linked with crop diversification. Cultivators in India used to grow multiple crops in their agricultural property during a crop season. It may be less heterogeneous in agricultural climate. The diversification level in India's crop pattern is measured using Gibbs & Martin’s Index of Diversification, providing a valuable substitute indicator to assess the crop diversity index within a specific region (Paul *et al* 2020). The crop Diversity Index is measured by equation no. (2) below.

$$C. D = 1 - \Sigma x^2 / \Sigma(x)^2 \tag{2}$$

Wherein, x represents the proportion of the overall cultivated land devoted to a specific crop

Following this approach, an increased Index value corresponds to a heightened diversification of cultivation, while a lower value indicates the opposite. If the index value approaches 1, it signifies an elevated level of diversification. Crop diversification has been witnessed in the study area by Bhatia’s method for principal crops such as Paddy, Mustard, Khesari, Til and Potato (Table 2) while 2014-15 of distinct zones in South 24 Parganas. They are organized in different categories from very high to low concentration regions. It has also been observed that crop concentration is dependent on the geomorphological setup of the blocks within the study area (Dhara 2016). The crop concentration index within the area under study is shown by (Table 2) below.

TABLE 2
CROP CONCENTRATION INDEX IN DIFFERENT BLOCKS OF SOUTH 24 PARGANAS AMID 2014-15

Sl. No.	Blocks of CD	Rice paddy	Mustard	Grass pea	Til	Potato
1	Bishnupur I	1.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	Bishnupur II	1.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
3	Thakurpukur/Maheshtala	1.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
4	Budge Budge I	1.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
5	Budge- Budge II	1.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
6	Jaynagar I	0.86	5.13	2.48	2.71	2.21
7	Jaynagar II	1.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
8	Sonarpur	1.06	0.38	0.00	0.00	0.00
9	Bhangar I	0.95	2.38	0.02	4.17	1.26
10	Bhangar II	0.85	7.04	0.09	3.16	5.4
11	Baruipur	1.03	0.00	1.74	0.00	0.00
12	Kultali	0.74	4.25	6.30	19.34	4.82
13	Canning I	1.03	0.00	1.02	0.00	0.53
14	Canning II	0.89	13.60	13.60	0.00	13.61
15	Mograhat I	1.04	0.04	0.68	0.01	0.33

16	Mograhat II	1.02	0.14	0.30	0.00	0.62
17	Gosaba	1.05	0.13	0.08	0.35	0.27
18	Basanti	1.05	0.08	0.02	0.00	0.00
19	Mandirabazar	0.99	0.00	3.73	0.00	0.98
20	Falta	1.04	0.00	1.09	0.00	0.00
21	Kulpi	0.99	1.44	3.21	0.04	0.00
22	Diamond Harbour I	0.89	0.44	9.41	0.04	0.81
23	Diamond Harbour II	0.92	0.00	8.58	0.00	0.00
24	Kakdwip	0.99	0.00	3.83	0.00	0.00
25	Mathurapur I	1.00	0.34	2.59	0.00	0.90
26	Mathurapur II	0.99	0.09	0.51	0.02	0.00
27	Patharpratima	1.01	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.15
28	Sagar	1.04	0.104	0.56	0.61	0.19
29	Namkhana	1.03	0.04	1.22	0.00	0.13

The data underscores the predominant role of Paddy being the primary farming in South 24 Parganas, cultured extensively across all zones. Remarkably profuse concentrations are evident in several blocks, including Thakurpukur/Maheshtala, Falta, Budge-Budge-I, Mograhat-I, Budge-Budge-II, Mograhat-II, Sonarpur, Bishnupur-I, Baruipur, Bishnupur-II, Canning-I, Mandirbazar, Jaynagar-II, Mathurapur-I, Kulpi, Mathurapur-II, Patharpratima, Kakdwip, Basanti, Gosaba, Namkhana, Sagar, among others. Diamond Harbour-II and Bhangar-I blocks exhibit a high concentration, while Canning-II, Bhangar-II, Jaynagar-I, and D. Harbour-I blocks demonstrate a moderate concentration. Notably, the Kultali zone displays the minimal presence of rice.

Grass pea is the second most notable crop, grown in the majority of areas. D. Harbour-I and D. Harbour-II have the maximum growth, in comparison maximum growth in Kultali. Moderate concentrations are observed in Jaynagar-I, Canning-II, Mandirbazar, Mathurapur-I, Kakdwip, and Kulpi. Certain blocks, such as Bishnupur-I, Budge-Budge-I, Bishnupur-II, Jaynagar-II, Thakurpukur/Maheshtala, Budge-Budge-II, and do not engage in Grass pea cultivation.

Mustard is another crucial crop, cultivated in 16 out of 29 blocks, with the highest concentration among Kultali, Jaynagar-II and Bhangar-II exhibiting relatively elevated concentrations, while Bhangar I shows a moderate concentration. Lower concentrations are observed in Gosaba, Canning-II, Kulpi, Basanti, Patharpratima, D. Harbour I, Namkhana, Mograhat II Mograhat I, Mathurapur I, Sagar and Mathurapur-II,

Potato is significant, grown in an equal quantity of zones similar to Mustard. Bhangar-II and Canning-II demonstrate very high concentrations, while Jaynagar-I, Bhangar-I, and Kultali exhibit relatively high concentrations. Moderate concentrations are found at, Mograhat-I, Canning-I, Mograhat-II, Mandirbazar, Mathurapur-I, and Diamond Harbour I, and lower concentrations in Sagar, Namkhana, Patharpratima, Gosaba, and Mathurapur-II. The heightened concentrations in these blocks are attributed to favourable agro-climatic conditions conducive to agriculture.

Crop diversification is a valuable aspect of determining the most suitable crops at a particular region. Essentially, it signifies the cultivation of a variety of farming in a given locality, contributing to increased agricultural output. The purpose is to provide a broader selection for cultivating various crops in a particular area, thereby expanding production activities across different crops and mitigating risks. Diversification measures for each block in South 24 Parganas were determined using Gibbs & Martin's approach (Table 5). The derived index values led to the classification of all blocks into categories of very high, high, medium, and low diversification.

A very high level of crop diversification is prominent in Kultali, Kulpi, D. Harbour-I, D. Harbour-II, Jaynagar-I, Jaynagar-II, Canning-I, Canning-II, and Bhangar-II blocks. A relatively high level of crop diversification is observed in Mathurapur-I, Mathurapur-II, Mograhat-I, Falta, Budge-Budge-II, Bishnupur-II, Thakurpukur-Maheshtala, and Baruipur. Moderate diversification is found in Bhangar-I, Budge-Budge-I, Bishnupur-I, Mograhat-II, Mandirbazar, and Gosaba blocks. Sagar, Namkhana, Kakdwip, Sonarpur Patharpratima, Basanti, and Jaynagar-II, blocks fall into the category of the low farming diversification region. (Table 3)

TABLE 3
CROP DIVERSIFICATION CATEGORIZATION AT THE BLOCK LEVEL IN SOUTH 24 PARGANAS DURING THE 2014-15 SEASON

Serial No.	Blocks (C.D)	Crop Diversification Index
1	Bishnupur I	0.22
2	Bishnupur II	0.43
3	Thakurpukur-Maheshtala	0.47
4	Budge Budge I	0.23
5	Budge- Budge II	0.46

6	Jaynagar-I	0.54
7	Jaynagar-II	0.02
8	Sonarpur	0.01
9	Bhangar I	0.31
10	Bhangar II	0.63
11	Baruipur	0.42
12	Kultali	0.64
13	Canning I	0.53
14	Canning-II	0.62
15	Mograhat I	0.45
16	Mograhat II	0.31
17	Gosaba	0.25
18	Basanti	0.05
19	Mandirabazar	0.23
20	Falta	0.40
21.	Kulpi	0.55
22	Diamond Harbour I	0.67
23	Diamond Harbour II	0.60
24	Kakdwip	0.11
25	Mathurapur I	0.41
26	Mathurapur II	0.46
27	Patharpratima	0.14
28	Sagar	0.04
29	Namkhana	0.05

It has been found that crop intensity in the study area is quite satisfactory but crop diversification at some places is quite low. Paddy is the primary crop that has been yielded at South 24 Parganas. Other crops like Khesari, mustard, potato, and til are also produced plenty. But trend analysis reveals that production of food grains like Aus, and Aman has decreased over decades whereas Boro is increasing. Production of non-food grains like linseed will also be enhanced. The pattern of crop yield in the study area will be shifted due to various reasons like temperature, rainfall, saline water intrusion from BoB, and reduction of fertility rate of the soil. So, the challenge of sustainable agriculture can be represented in Fig 5.

V. PROBLEM FACED IN IRRIGATION DUE TO IMPURE WATER IN THE SALINE-PRONE STUDY AREA

Distance between the centre of South 24 Parganas from BoB is approximately 61 Km which is very close. Moreover, there are some blocks in South 24 Parganas like Sagar which is positioned approximately only 2.55 Km from BoB. From the various literature available it has been observed that seawater ingress takes place into the main aquifer of South 24 Parganas from BoB.

Moreover, lots of rivers are present in South 24 Parganas like Matla River, Raimangal River, Bidhyadhari River, Piyali River, Hooghly River, Muri Ganga River, Gosaba River, Thakuran River, Saptamukhi River Hatania Doania River. These rivers originated close to BoB and are therefore saline prone (Ghosh *et al* 2021, Kaur 2020, Sarkar *et al* 2021).

Hence, the irrigation water for agricultural purposes in the study area is not of satisfactory quality (Bandyopadhyay 2017, Mukherjee *et al* 2021, Nath *et al* 2021). For judgement of aquaquality, two parameters of saline water in the study area have been taken such as Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) and Chloride for the last 5 years i.e. from 2017-2018 to 2021-2022. The data have been collected from WB Public Health Directorate (WBPHEd) website

Out of 29 blocks data of 28 blocks have been obtained for the duration of the last 5 years. TDS and chloride values in the pumping well of 28 blocks in South 24 Parganas for the year 2017-2018, 2018-2019, 2019-2020, 2020-2021, and 2021-2022 have been represented in Fig no. 5, Fig no.6, Fig no.7, Fig 8, Fig 9 respectively.

Fig 5 TDS and Chloride values in pumping wells in the study area for the year 2017-2018

It is pertinent that the quality of irrigation water is substandard when compared to consumable water. Nevertheless, for a standard of comparison, the consumable water specification IS 10500:2012 has been considered. According to IS 10500: 2012, the tolerable range of Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) is five hundred (500) ppm for potable water, and for Chloride, it is 250 ppm. Permissible limits are not considered since alternate sources like surface as well as subsurface water are available.

From Figure 5, it is evident that subsurface water from most blocks of South 24 Parganas has deteriorated in quality from the TDS perspective. Maximum degradation has been observed at Sonarpur, Kultali, Canning-1, Basanti, Mathurapur-2, and Patharpratima. These blocks are severely affected by seawater intrusion and are unsuitable for use as irrigation water. The groundwater in these locations is unfit for agriculture from the TDS standpoint. Conversely, groundwater from Mahestala, Budge Budge-2, Jaynagar-1, Bhangar-2, Canning-2, Kulpi, Kakdwip, Mathurapur-1, Sagar is considered safe for irrigation use from the TDS perspective. Only 9 blocks out of the obtained data from 28 blocks, representing approximately 32.14%, are declared safe for irrigation water. The remaining blocks are also impacted by seawater ingress and are unsuitable for sustaining agricultural growth. Therefore, five years ago, in the year 2017-2018, almost 67.86% (2/3) of the total blocks were rendered unfit for irrigation water.

From Figure 5, it has been observed that subsurface water from Bishnupur-1, Bishnupur-2, Mahestala, Budge-1, Budge Budge-2, Jaynagar-2, Jaynagar-1, Baruipur, Kultali, Mograhat-1, Mograhat-2, Basanti, Mandirabazar, Falta, Kulpi, Diamond Harbour-1, Diamond Harbour-2, Mathurapur-1, Mathurapur-2, Sagar, and Namkhana is safe for irrigation water from the Chloride perspective. Subsurface water from 21 blocks out of 28 blocks, approximately 75%, is free from chloride attack. Therefore, the study area is more affected by TDS than Chloride in the year 2017-2018. The blocks most affected by Chloride attack include Sonarpur, Canning-1, Canning-2, Kakdwip, Patharpratima, Bhangar-1, Bhangar-2, etc. Consequently, groundwater from these blocks is unsuitable for agricultural purposes. In the years 2017-2018, it has been depicted that subsurface water from Mahestala, Budge-2, Jaynagar-1, Kulpi, Mathurapur-1, and Sagar are free from both TDS and Chloride contamination.

Fig 6 TDS and Chloride values in pumping wells in the study area for the year 2018-2019

From Figure 6, it has been observed that in the year 2018-2019, subsurface water from locations such as Bishnupur 2, Mahestala, Jayanagar-1, Jayanagar-2, Bhangar-2, Canning-2, Kakdwip, Mathurapur-2, Sagar, were uncontaminated by Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) according to IS 10500:2012. Hence, approximately 32.14% of locations in South 24 Parganas maintained good-quality water for irrigation, consistent with the previous year. The remaining 67.86% of locations in South 24 Parganas were affected by TDS contamination in groundwater during the year 2018-2019.

It is also observed that blocks like Bishnupur-1, Mahestala, Budge-2, Jayanagar-2, Bhangar-1, Bhangar-2, Baruipur, Kultali, Canning-1, Canning-2, Mograhat-1, Mograhat-2, Basanti, Mandirabazar, Falta, Kulpi, Kakdwip, Mathurapur-1, Mathurapur-2, Sagar, Namkhana were free from Chloride contamination in the year 2018-2019, accounting for 21 out of 28 blocks. Therefore, approximately 64.28% of locations in South 24 Parganas were devoid of contamination from the Chloride perspective according to IS 10500:2012. The remaining 35.72% of locations in the study area were affected by chloride, representing an increase from 25% in the previous year. Thus, the trend of groundwater contamination due to seawater ingress and other anthropogenic activities is escalating year by year.

Fig 7 TDS and Chloride values in pumping wells in the study area for the year 2019-2020

From Figure 7, it has been noted that blocks in South 24 Parganas, such as Bishnupur 2, Mahestala, Jayanagar-1, Jayanagar-2, Bhangar-2, Canning-2, Kakdwip, Mathurapur-2, Sagar, were free from TDS contamination in groundwater. Therefore, a total of 32.14% of blocks were unaffected by TDS concerns according to IS 10500:2012 in the year 2019-2020. The remaining 67.86% of blocks were impacted by seawater injection into the aquifer, consistent with the previous year.

It has also been observed that blocks in South 24 Parganas, like Bishnupur- Bishnupur-1, Bishnupur-2, Mahestala, Budge-1, Budge Budge-2, Jaynagar-2, Jaynagar-1, Baruipur, Kultali, Mograhat-1, Mograhat-2, Basanti, Mandirabazar, Falta, Kulpi, Diamond Harbour-1, Diamond Harbour-2, Mathurapur-1, Mathurapur-2, Sagar, and Namkhana, were not contaminated by Chloride according to IS10500:2012 in the year 2019-2020, accounting for 21 out of 28 blocks (75%). Therefore, 25% of the blocks were affected by Chloride contamination, mirroring the previous year's trend.

Fig 8 TDS and Chloride values in pumping wells in the study area for the year 2020-2021

From Fig 8 it has been observed that groundwater from blocks viz. Bishnupur 2, Mahestala, Jayanagar-1, Jayanagar-2, Bhangar-2, Canning-2, Kakdwip, Mathurapur-2, and Sagar were not polluted from seawater intrusion from the TDS point of view according to IS10500: 2012. So the percentage of unaffected blocks in the year 2020-2021 was the same as the year before which is 32.14%.

It has also been observed that blocks in South 24 Parganas, such as Bishnupur-1, Mahestala, Budge-2, Jayanagar-2, Bhangar-1, Bhangar-2, Baruipur, Kultali, Canning-1, Canning-2, Mograhat-1, Mograhat-2, Basanti, Mandirabazar, Falta, Kulpi, Kakdwip, Mathurapur-1, Mathurapur-2, Sagar, Namkhana, were free from Chloride contamination according to IS10500:2012 in the year 2019-2020, encompassing 21 out of 28 blocks (75%). Therefore, 25% of the blocks exhibited Chloride contamination, as was the case in the preceding year.

Fig 9 TDS and Chloride values in pumping wells in the study area for the year 2021-2022

From Figure 9, it has been noted that subsurface water in locations such as Bisnupur-2, Jaynagar-1, Bhangar-2, Mograhat-2, Kakdwip, Mathurapur-1, Mathurapur-2, Sagar was not tainted by seawater injection into the aquifer, based on the Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) perspective according to IS 10500:2012. Therefore, in the year 2021-2022, 28.57% of blocks continued to have good quality irrigation water concerning TDS compliance. The remaining 71.43% of locations were found to be contaminated with TDS during the same period.

Similarly, it has been observed that blocks in South 24 Parganas, such as Mahestala, Budge Budge-2, Jayanagar-1, Jayanagar-2, Bhangar-1, Bhangar-2, Baruipur, Kultali, Canning-1, Canning-2, Mograhat-1, Mograhat-2, Basanti, Mandirabazar, Falta, Kulpi, Diamond Harbour-1, Diamond Harbour-2, Kakdwip, Mathurapur -1, Sagar, Namkhana, have exhibited satisfactory irrigation water quality concerning Chloride levels based on IS 10500:2012. Therefore, 16 out of 28 blocks demonstrated good-quality subsurface irrigation water as per the standard code. Consequently, in the year 2021-22, it has been observed that only 57.14% of blocks possessed satisfactory quality irrigation water, while the remaining 42.86% had groundwater unsuitable for agricultural use.

VI. TREND ANALYSIS OF GROUNDWATER CONTAMINATION IN SOUTH 24 PARGANAS FROM 2017-2018 TO 2021-2022

For the discussion held above the status of pollution of subsurface water in different blocks of South 24 Parganas has been graphically represented in Fig 10.

Fig 10 Percentage of blocks affected in its groundwater due to seawater ingress from 2017-2018 to 2021-2022 from TDS and Chloride point of view

From Fig 10 it has been noticed that the percentage of blocks in South 24 Parganas was constant from 2017-2018 from both TDS (i.e. 67.86%) and Chloride (25%) points of view from 2017-2018 to 2020-2021. The rate of pollution has been increasing at a high rate in the last 5 years. Furthermore, it has been noted that groundwater contamination has significantly risen since 2021-2022, when around (2/3rd) blocks and (2/5th) blocks were polluted by TDS and Chloride respectively. If the situation is not mitigated now then in future there will be no pure irrigation water will be available. Since agronomy is the most suitable for the study area both the economic system and daily life of the habitats of the study area will be in danger.

VII. REMEDIAL MEASUREMENT OF GROUNDWATER AND SURFACE TO MAKE IT FIT FOR CULTIVATION

The process of desalting saltwater is undertaken to eliminate dissolved minerals, such as salts, from brackish feed water. The maximum adopted methodology for the interchange of brackish water into pure water for irrigation are a) Solar distillation methodology, b) Reverse osmosis (RO), c) Electro dialysis, and d) Freezing method (Tuteja 2017, Ramesh 2015, Lakshmi 2000). RO utilizes pressure as the driving factor for its membrane process, In this process, a feed stream is pushed through a semi-permeable membrane under pressure, resulting in a separation between two aqueous streams—one rich in salt and the other with reduced salt content.

Water penetrates through the filter under implied pressure, resulting in the retention of impurities. As a consequence, a permeate stream with a reduced salt density is generated, while a dense brine remains on the source side where the stress surpasses the osmosis, retaining the salt (Sanchez et al., 2019). The Reverse Osmosis (RO) method is effective in diminishing TDS density by until 45,000mg/L, making it suitable for desalinating both saliferous water and seawater. Seawater RO facilities can opt for either seawater wells (beach wells) or surface water, which involves an open seawater intake, as their source water source. (Kabeel 2015).

Membrane distillation (MD) is a heat-induced segregation process involving the transition from aqua to vapour on either side of the filter and the vapourisation of vapour to aqua on the opposite part. The use of excess heat power as solar power enhances

MD as a maximum favourable segregation method for industrial utilisation. MD is applied in 4 distinct configurations, viz. air gap membrane distillation (AGMD), direct contact membrane distillation (DCMD), sweeping gas membrane distillation (SGMD) and vacuum membrane distillation (VMD). The integration of solar energy with heat-influenced membrane filtration for consumable water production, using minimal waste thermal power, is a trending focus of study in numerous study-related institutions.

Solar power offers a simple, cost-effective, and economical solution for converting saline water into fresh water, making it particularly useful for hamlets, countryside, and regions with low economic status. There are two categories of solar-powered membrane distillation (MD): Explicit and implicit systems. In explicit systems, both heat acquisition and desalination occur automatically on the same gadget such as a solar still. By the implicit method, the system is divided into two module systems – a sun ray collector and a segregation unit. The sunray collector, which can take various forms like a plate which is a flat, cleared tube, photovoltaic cell, or sun concentrator, is coupled with a distillation unit using the vaporization and condensing norms. Latest advancements indicate that sun rays -powered desalting processes outperform alternative membrane desalination technologies (Patel 2021).

Freeze separation involves the freezing of salt water to create pristine crystals, that must be separated from the pickling solution and subsequently liquefied to obtain consumable water. However, this technique is still in its early stages of development. Ion-exchange membrane desalination is the nearby relative of electrochemical deionization procedures and its successful application in brackish water desalination. Given its resemblance to CDI techniques, this one is valuable to analyse this technology from two viewpoints. At first, electro-dialysis stands as an industry-standard water treatment technology. Next, there are similarities amidst CDI and ED processes, especially regarding migration in solution and through membranes, which are noteworthy for examination and comparison.

Using hybrid technology is found to be more effective as no single technology addresses all issues. Equipment and technology advancements are progressing, and suggestions are based on the best available science and technology. Combining techniques or hybrid methods has evolved due to the synergy of various technologies. Researchers focus on synergistic RO technology, which refines filtration through filter processes, purifying water for diverse uses.

In RO technology, pre-treatment is essential to avoid problems like fouling and membrane disturbances. Conventional pre-treatment involves the use of chemicals such as coagulants, flocculants, acids, and disinfectants. Physicochemical aspects are evaluated for water purification using coagulation and flocculation, including green coagulants. Plant-based coagulants like cactus, moringa oleifera and aloe vera, show promise, with moringa oleifera at 15 mg/l intake and pH 6 exhibiting high effectiveness.

Disinfection methods like chlorine treatment are common, but de-chlorination is necessary for pre-treatment of the final yield. Superchlorination is known but has limitations in potable aqua applications. Recent hybrid technologies such as ED-RO offer separation and concentration benefits, with reduced energy usage and nil discharge. Combining techniques provides a comprehensive solution to water purification challenges and conservation.

Testing the proposed hybrid technology on contaminated groundwater in the laboratory is crucial for clearer results. UV is commonly used as a final cleansing stage to separate contaminants, viruses, and bacteria for improved outcomes (Chakraborty *et al* 2023).

The shortage of freshwater is a current global challenge. Various desalination techniques have been proposed to obtain freshwater from seawater. However, traditional methods face technical constraints like high energy ingestion, costly operation, and restricted system longevity. It has explored the viability of utilizing halophytes as innovative techniques for desalting highly concentrated saline water over extended periods. The study delved into the physiological traits of marine water purification within the root system of the Rhizophora mangrove in terms of plant fluid dynamics perspective. Rhizophora can thrive in saline water, regulating salt levels inside a specific filtration threshold. The root exhibits a layered and tiered pore arrangement within the skin's outer layer. Most Na⁺ ions being separated within the initial sub-stratum of the outermost covering. The effective prevention of Na⁺ ion passage is linked to the elevated surface zeta potential of the initial layer. Additionally, the second layer, characterized by microporous structures, contributes to the filtration of Na⁺ ions. This research sheds light on the methods of aqua filtration through halophyte base, laying the groundwork for the improvement of an innovative biomimetic desalination technique (Kim *et al* 2016).

Agronomic practices are crucial for enhancing crop productivity, but they may not suffice under changing climates, negatively impacting crop growth and soil quality. Preserving resources like water becomes challenging. Hence, adopting adaptive methods such as crop rotation, mixed crop-livestock farming, mulching, agroforestry, push-pull systems and intercropping for pest control is essential (Dubey *et al* 2020) Diagrammatically the entire process is represented in Fig 11.

Fig 11 Flow chart of Sustainable Agriculture

VIII. CONCLUSION

South 24 Parganas, a key division in WB, holds significance as the highest in area and second-highest in population in the state. Agriculture is a vital occupation, benefitting from the presence of alluvium soil, allowing for the cultivation of various crops.

Paddy crop has the highest intensity, and other major crops include Mustard, Khesari, Til, and Potato. Crop diversification is notable, but the coastal area is susceptible to salinity because of its closeness to the BoB. This salinity affects both surface and subsurface water, reducing irrigation water quality and soil fertility, and leading to poor crop growth.

The groundwater quality has worsened since 2021-2022, making it unsuitable for agriculture (Bhat *et al* 2023). To ensure sustainable agriculture, proposed methods include applying hybrid technology to brackish water, adopting adaptive agriculture, desalination of salty water, and using distillation techniques on saline water. Among these, solar-powered desalination is recommended for its economic, cost-effective, and simple solution, especially beneficial for rural communities.

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